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- ✓ TABIIY FANLAR
- ✓ SIYOSIY FANLAR
- ✓ IJTIMOY FANLAR

- ✓ IQTISOD FANLARI
- ✓ TEXNIKA FANLARI
- ✓ TIBBIYOT FANLARI
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THE MODERN METHODS OF TREATMENT OF DIABETIC NEPHROPATHY

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Abstract: *Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a disease that accompanies a person for a long period of time. The greatest danger of diabetes is undoubtedly associated with complications that develop due to its damaging effects on blood vessels, particularly diabetic nephropathy (DN), which develops in approximately 20.1% of patients with diabetes of the 1st type and 6.3% of patients with diabetes of the 2nd type. In patients with diabetes of the 2nd type, diabetic nephropathy ranks third among causes of death after diseases of the cardiovascular system and oncological pathologies. There are many mechanisms of damaging effects of various factors that play a key role in the development of renal pathology in diabetes. We focused on a more detailed examination of the effect of renin-angiotensin-aldosterone (RAAS), direct damaging effects of hyperglycemia, polyol glucose metabolism, and hyperlipidemia, endothelial growth factor (VEGF) and transforming growth factor β (TGF- β). Based on the knowledge of the pathogenesis of diabetic nephropathy, very promising targets have been identified for the correction of this pathology.*

Key words: *diabetic nephropathy, hyperglycemia, diabetic kidney disease.*

СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ МЕТОДЫ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ДИАБЕТИЧЕСКОЙ НЕФРОПАТИИ.

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Аннотация: Сахарный диабет (СД) – заболевание, сопровождающее человека в течение длительного периода времени. Наибольшую опасность СД, несомненно, связаны с осложнениями, развивающимися вследствие его повреждающего воздействия на сосуды, в частности с диабетической нефропатией (ДН), которая развивается примерно у 20,1% больных СД 1-го типа и у 6,3% больных СД 1-го типа и 6,3% больных СД 1-го типа. 2-й тип. У больных сахарным диабетом 2-го типа диабетическая нефропатия занимает третье место среди причин смерти после заболеваний сердечно-сосудистой системы и онкологических патологий. Существует множество механизмов повреждающего действия различных факторов, играющих ключевую роль в развитии патологии почек при сахарном диабете. Мы сосредоточились на более детальном изучении влияния ренин-ангиотензин-альдостерона (РААС), прямых повреждающих эффектов гипергликемии, метаболизма полиоловой глюкозы и гиперлипидемии, эндотелиального фактора роста (VEGF) и трансформирующего фактора роста β (TGF- β). На основании знаний о патогенезе диабетической нефропатии определены весьма перспективные цели коррекции этой патологии.

Ключевые слова: диабетическая нефропатия, гипергликемия, диабетическая болезнь почек.

Effects on biochemical and structural changes in renal membranes. At present, the search is underway for promising drugs that can affect the structure and biochemical composition of the basement membranes of the renal glomeruli. One of such drugs, which has already passed experimental and clinical trials, is sulodexide (Alfa Wassermann, Italy), which is a low-molecular-weight heparin. This drug, without affecting the blood coagulation system, is able to increase the content of heparan sulfate in the glomerular membranes, restore the selective permeability of the renal filter and prevent the development of sclerotic processes in the kidney tissue. We tested this drug in 18 patients with insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus (9 people with microalbuminuria and 9 people with proteinuria). The drug was administered intramuscularly once a day, 5 days a week (with a 2-day break) for 3 weeks. In 89% of patients, a significant antiproteinuric effect was noted, reaching its maximum by the end of the treatment period, and protein excretion in the urine decreased in patients with both microalbuminuria and proteinuria. This effect persisted for the next 6 weeks after discontinuation of treatment, although there was some tendency to re-increase albuminuria. In addition, the antiatherogenic effect of sulodexide was noted: the atherogenic coefficient of serum decreased. When assessing the condition of the fundus of the eye in patients treated with sulodexide, a positive trend was revealed in the non-proliferative and preproliferative stages of diabetic retinopathy and stabilization of the process in the proliferative stage of retinopathy. Thus, this drug had a beneficial effect not only on the course of DN, but also on the wall of retinal vessels. Another inevitable consequence of hyperglycemia is non-enzymatic glycosylation of the structural proteins of the glomerular basement membrane, which also leads to disruption of their configuration and loss of normal selective permeability to proteins. To interrupt the non-enzyme glycosylation reaction, the drug aminoguanidine is successfully used in the experiment, which irreversibly reacts with glycosylation products, thereby stopping this process. However, no clinical trials of this drug have been conducted to date. Increased glucose metabolism along the polyol pathway under the influence of the enzyme aldose reduction leads to the accumulation of sorbitol (osmotically active substance) in insulin-independent tissues, also contributing to the development of late complications of diabetes mellitus. To interrupt this process, the clinic uses drugs from the group of aldose reductase inhibitors (tolrestat, statil). A number of studies have demonstrated a decrease in albuminuria in patients with type 1 diabetes mellitus receiving aldose reductase inhibitors. However, the clinical efficacy of these drugs is more pronounced in the treatment of diabetic neuropathy

or retinopathy and less so in the treatment of DN. This may be due to the fact that the polyol pathway of glucose metabolism plays a smaller role in the pathogenesis of diabetic kidney damage than the vessels of other non-insulin-dependent tissues.

Effects on vasoactive factors of vascular endothelium and platelets. The vascular endothelium and platelets are the cells most sensitive to the effects of high glucose concentrations. Endothelial cell dysfunction consists in the overproduction of biologically active substances involved in the processes of intravascular coagulation and regulation of vascular tone (endothelin-1, endothelial relaxation factor, prostacyclin). Platelet dysfunction in uncompensated diabetes mellitus is manifested by high production of coagulation factors, as well as excessive release of thromboxane A₂ (TCA₂), which causes vasospasm and platelet hyperaggregation. All of these endothelial and platelet factors, causing spasm and thrombotic occlusion of blood vessels, contribute to the development and progression of both micro- and macroangiopathies in diabetes mellitus. Therefore, drug correction of the activity of these factors could help prevent the rapid progression of late vascular complications of diabetes mellitus. Medications that correct the synthesis of vasoactive endothelial factors (endothelin-1 and endothelial relaxation factor) are at the stage of experimental development and in the future have a real chance to take a leading place in the treatment of diabetic angiopathies. At the same time, drugs that affect the prostacyclin-thromboxane system have already been developed and are widely used in nephrological practice for the treatment of chronic renal diseases. In the practice of diabetologists, these drugs have not yet been widely used, although their use for the treatment of diabetic angiopathies (and, above all, DN) is pathogenetically justified. For example, TCA₂ not only causes vasospasm and platelet hyperaggregation, but also has a direct damaging effect on the structure and function of the kidneys, provoking the development of proteinuria and accelerating the process of sclerosing of renal tissue. In this regard, it seemed expedient to investigate the effect of a drug that blocks excess production of TCA₂ on renal function in patients with DN. For this purpose, we used ibustrin (Pharmacia, Switzerland), which is an inhibitor of the enzyme cyclooxygenase, which is involved in the formation of TCA₂ from arachidonic acid. Treatment was provided to 16 patients with insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus with proteinuric stage DN (proteinuria did not exceed 1 g/day). All patients also had different stages of diabetic retinopathy and impaired blood supply to the lower extremities, diagnosed by Doppler sonography of the arteries of the feet. Ibustrin was prescribed 1 tablet 2 times a day (400 mg/day) for 3 months. At the end of the course of treatment, there was an improvement in renal function: glomerular

filtration rate increased in 13 (81%) patients, daily proteinuria decreased in 12 (75%) patients. The efficacy of treatment against retinopathy directly depended on the stage of pathological changes in the fundus vessels: among patients with the non-proliferative stage of retinopathy, improvement was noted in 83%, in the presence of the preproliferative stage — in 40% of patients, but in patients with the proliferative stage there was practically no positive dynamics. Increased blood flow in the lower extremities during treatment with ibustrin was observed in 62% of patients. Such a high efficacy of ibustrin in the treatment of vascular complications of diabetes mellitus, found in our study, can be explained by the timely initiation of the use of this drug, i.e., at relatively early stages of the development of angiopathies (in proteinuria not exceeding 1 g/day; in the non-proliferative or preproliferative stage of retinopathy; in the initial decrease in blood flow in the lower extremities). In the later stages of vascular complications, the efficacy of the drug would appear to be minimal. Thus, in our study. The assumption of the efficacy of the use of drugs blocking the synthesis of TCA2 in the complex treatment of diabetic angiopathies, especially when prescribed at the early stages of vascular complications, has been confirmed.

Purpose: to study common complications and preventive measures for diabetes mellitus in people of different ages.

Materials and methods: studying complications of the disease, data were collected from patients Endocrinological center for Samarkand the years. The data of 30 patients were studied, of which 14 were men and 16 women.

Study results: The most common complication among patients was diabetic nephropathy in 15 patients. According to the results of the study, untimely treatment of diabetic nephropathy leads to chronic renal failure. The initial signs of nephropathy were an increased amount of urination, frequent increases in blood pressure, swelling, and deterioration in health. Instrumental laboratory tests showed an increase in creatinine. Of the 15 patients with diabetic nephropathy, 5 patients are over 47 years old, 7 patients are from 30 to 45 years old and 2 patients are from 25 to 30 years old. Treatment began with a conservative method; in 4 patients, conservative treatment did not show results and hemodialysis was prescribed.

Conclusion. Summarizing all of the above, we can conclude that the pathogenesis of the development of DN is quite complex and has a number of its own features. This problem has spread all over the world and has not lost its relevance today. Treatment of the last stage of DN is not only a complex process, but also, due to some economic aspects, very expensive. It's much easier to prevent vascular complications and try to prevent the disease from progressing to end-stage renal failure, how to treat patients with chronic renal

failure using hemodialysis. Therefore, despite detailed study existing problem, question of correction nephropathy remains open to this day.

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Tom 02. Son. 04. 2024	Vol. 02. Iss. 04. 2024	Том 02. Вып. 04. 2024

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